

Dami Jackfruit: Can It Be Made Into Jackfruit - Floss?

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Abstract:- The community in Indonesia knows about the Floss or Abon as a food menu, either as a side dish for breakfast, lunch, and dinner. People are familiar with shredded raw materials from beef, chicken, fish, and even buffalo. This study aims to use “Dami Jackfruit” to reduce waste that is rarely used by the community because we know that people consider “Dami Jackfruit” as waste that is not suitable for consumption because it does not have a sweet taste like Jackfruit. The research method used in this research is the experimental method and the organoleptic tests to find out the quality of the Abon, through a hedonic test. The results stated that 100% Dami Jackfruit Floss was acceptable to the community in the Taste category.

Keywords:- Jackfruit, Dami Jackfruit, Floss.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the modern era, people are increasingly curious by looking for and finding new things in culinary terms. The presence of the technology advance plays an important role in carrying out creativity and innovation in processing foodstuffs or processed materials, such as the manufacture of Floss from various materials it can consume.

In keeping up with the growing availability of food products, it requires product development and innovation, thereby earning disposable income [1]

Floss or Abon, a well-known word in Indonesia is a processed product, and is widely known by various levels of society, both children and adults because of its delicious taste. So far, people are familiar with shredded raw materials from beef, chicken, fish, and even buffalo. Besides being able to be used as a side dish for rice, floss can also be used as a filling, sprinkle, or complementary food products, such as stuffing Lemper, Cake sprinkles, Bread, and others.

One type of processed product made from Beef that is durable and favored by people from various circles is Beef floss. Beef floss is a type of dry food made from beef that is boiled, shredded, sprinkled with spices, fried, and then squeezed until it dries [2].

The problem with Beef floss production is the high production cost. The use of beef raw materials for 1 kilogram can produce 0.5 kg of minced meat. Therefore, the filling of beef floss uses additional ingredients or even replaces the Beef floss with other foods that can be consumed [2].

Jackfruit plant is a plant that is often found in a fairly large yard because this plant grows large with hanging fruit. Jackfruit Toaya Jackfruit Varieties and Varieties Palupi in the

Sulawesi region the middle is a national superior variety based on the government (SK.MENTAN RI NO. 458/KPTS/PD 210/9/2003). This variety has advantages, sweet taste, thick and crunchy flesh [3].

Today, there has been a worldwide awareness of the use of industrial wastes to increase the important nutritional elements including vitamins, dietary fiber, and protein. [4].

Nevertheless, Dami Jackfruit has not been used as raw material, therefore, it is due time to incorporate the Dami Jackfruit as a source of nutrients for human nutrition as well as to be used as a daily food as a side dish to accompany rice, and then it can be used as a new home industry so that the existence of this jackfruit straw shredded industry will create new jobs.

This study has two problems; Can Dami Jackfruit become an essential ingredient for making Floss? Is the floss of 100% Dami Jackfruit acceptable to the community?

Based on these issues and the two objectives of this study, namely to utilize unused waste into a product that has value and marketability. The existence of new ideas as business opportunities for the community. There is an addition to the diversity of food processing made from Dami Jackfruit.

II. MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research method used in this research is the experimental method. Experimental research is research that aims to find possible causal relationships by treating specifically the phenomenon that is the object of research [5]

Experimental design is a step that needs to be done before empirical activities so that the necessary data obtained simply will lead to objective analysis, and conclusions on the issues will be discussed [6].

This study was a comparative study that used 100% Dami Jackfruit floss and also 75% The Floss of Demi Jackfruit, and 25% Beef Floss

This research used organoleptic tests to observe the quality of the Floss, through a hedonic test to ask for responses about the preference. Organoleptic is called sensory test, one of the oldest means of quality control, the principle is an essential part of the mandatory assessment of food standards, and the process of perception of sensory quality [7].

The research instrument was in the form of an organoleptic test questionnaire to obtain data on people's preferences in receiving the Floss of Dami Jackfruit.

Questionnaires allocated to the public called panelists to carry out organoleptic tests so that they could find out the level of preference for the products that were made. The number of panelists in this study was fifteen people. The data obtained from the questionnaire was used as a fundamental reference for thinking in discussing the results of the products studied.

Panelists will mark the number on the organoleptic test questionnaire regarding taste by the sense of taste and aroma with smell, color with sight, and then texture with touch.

a) Tools and Equipments

The tools used are:

- Knife. Knives are used for the peeling and chopping process. The knife used must be sharp.
- Spoon. The spoon used is a tablespoon made of stainless steel.
- Receptacle. The container can be a basin made of plastic or melamine. This tool is needed to accommodate raw materials resulting from stripping, placing materials, washing, or pulverizing.
- Cutting board. The cutting board can be used as a base for cutting/slicing. The cutting board used is made of plastic.
- Scales. Scales are used to measure the weight of raw materials and additives based on a predetermined formula. The scales used are digital scales.
- Measuring cup. The measuring cup is used to measure the liquid used such as coconut milk or oil. Measuring cups are made of plastic or glass.
- Grinder / Blender. A grinder is used to crush or grind spices that need to be ground.
- Gauze. This cloth is used to remove the water from the main ingredient that has been nailed and to squeeze the hot floss so that the oil comes out.
- Spatula. The spatula is used to stir or flatten the ingredients during the cooking process. The spatula used is a spatula made of stainless steel.
- Filter. The filter is used to filter the shredded after frying, the filter used is a stainless steel filter.
- Wok. The skillet is used for the seasoning cooking process. The size of the skillet used is adjusted to the amount of raw material being cooked. The skillet used is stainless steel.
- Steaming Pot. The steam key is used to steam the jackfruit straw and boil the meat.
- Stove. The stove is used as a heating device during the cooking process. The stove used is a gas stove.

b) Raw Material

The Table below shows the ingredients for making Dami Jackfruit Floss:

No	Item	Total
1	Jackfruit Straw	500 gr
2	Shallots	25 gr
3	Garlic	8 g
4	Coriander Powder	12 gr
5	Galangal	50 gr
6	bay leaves	1-2 sheets
7	Lemongrass	10 g
8	Sugar	100 gr
9	Salt	6 gr
10	Broth Powder	5 gr
11	Thick Coconut Milk	100 gr
12	Lime	10 gr
13	Cooking Oil	150 gr

Table 1: Dami Jackfruit 100%

No	Item	Total
1	Jackfruit Straw	375 gr
2	Beef floss	125 gr
3	Shallots	25 gr
4	Garlic	8 g
5	Coriander Powder	12 gr
6	Galangal	50 gr
7	bay leaves	1-2 sheets
8	Lemongrass	10 g
9	Sugar	100 gr
10	Salt	6 gr
11	Broth Powder	5 gr
12	Thick Coconut Milk	100 gr
13	Lime	10 gr
14	Cooking Oil	150 gr

Table 2.: Dami Jackfruit 75% and Beef floss 25%

c) Dami Jackfruit Processing

In the trial of making Floss Dami jackfruit, there are several stages/standard procedures for making the floss. Prepare the tools to be used and weigh the materials. Choose fruit Jackfruit Dami to determine product quality and peel the Jackfruit the action of separating the flesh from Dami, so it washes thoroughly. Then for thirty minutes steam it and boil Dami Jackfruit. After the steaming process is complete, squeeze it, compress it dry with a clean cloth, grate until the texture is fibrous, and then mashed. Add Coriander Powder, sugar, Broth Powder, lime, salt, and coconut milk. Then let stand for the spices to infuse, and then The Floss is shredded.

Remember, there are two ways to make the Floss. The first is 100% Dami Jackfruit Floss, and the second is 75% Dami Jackfruit Floss mixed with 25% Beef Floss, made separately.

Put the Floss into the cooking oil, and cook over low heat, gripping all the time up to cook. A characteristic feature of ripe the Floss is a rustling sound when kneaded. After the shredded Dami

Jackfruit is cold, press it down to remove the oil. Use a clean cloth to squeeze out any excess oil on the yarn, until it is totally dry.

III. THEORY

A. Floss or Abon

The community already knows the process of making abon which is done in the traditional way using a fork to slice the meat into the same size, and smaller ones [8].

Things that affect the Floss quality and durability are factors of the materials used, and the method of manufacture. In the steaming stage, the temperature is only up to reach the boiling point. The next stage is draining, the material to be made shredded, placed in a container wide enough to not accumulate so that the process even cooling. Don't do steaming temperature that is too high will reduce the quality and texture of the material. [8].

The Floss or Abon has long been known in the community as a food menu, either as a side dish for breakfast, lunch, and dinner. Usually, the Floss is served with rice, bread, or as an additional ingredient in the pastry industry. The Floss is a snack or side dish ready to eat that has high nutritional value because the raw materials consist of beef, chicken, and fish [9].

The Floss or Abon is a type of dry food with a distinctive shape, made from meat, boiled, sliced, seasoned, fried, and pressed [10].

The Floss or Abon is a preservation process, which is a combination of boiling or steaming and frying by adding spices, have color, aroma, texture, and taste the distinctive taste and has a shelf life long enough [11].

B. The Jackfruit

The Jackfruit comes from South India and advance to all other countries with tropical climates, including Indonesia. In some areas, Jackfruit has a different name. In Aceh, for example, jackfruit is known as Panaih. In Lampung, jackfruit is known as Lamasa or Malasa. In Java, it is called Nongko. In Gorontalo, it is known as Jackfruit or Langge. In Ambon is Anaane. And in Irian Jaya it is known as Nagnak or Krour [12]

Known Jackfruit as a multipurpose plant because all parts of the plant can be used for various purposes ranging from needs for food, housing, reforestation, livestock, industry, and even health. Jackfruit is included in plants that get priority to be developed in Multipurpose Tree Species Development Program Use (JPSG). Jackfruit tree selection as one of the horticultural crops, products processed is of high value, it plants has bright prospects as a supporter in the National Foreign Exchange Improvement Program and Food Diversification. [3]

Jackfruit plants are content with fruit flesh, seeds, straw or dami, and skin. The part of the jackfruit plant that is most widely used is the flesh of the fruit, when the fruit is ripe it has a distinctive aroma and sweet taste, so it is widely consumed directly, made in Jackfruit Sweets, Jackfruit Cake,

and others. Jackfruit seeds can be consumed by frying, boiling, or burning. The part of the Jackfruit that is most often not used, thrown away, or made into the best food is the straw or jackfruit dami. [13]

Dami jackfruit is part of the Jackfruit in the form of flowers that do not experience pollination. Dami Jackfruit is also called lint or straw. For jackfruit consumers, Dami is used as waste Jackfruit without any attempt to exploit it. In ripe jackfruit, Dami is thick and large and has a sweet taste that can be consumed [13]

On the Table below we can see that the nutrition of Dami Jackfruit.

No.	Nutrition	Jumlah
1.	Protein (%)	1,95
2.	Fat (%)	10,00
3.	Carbohidrat (%)	9,35
4.	Vit C (mg / 100 gr)	2,05
5.	Water (%)	65,12
6.	Fiber (%)	1,94

Table 3: Nutrition of Dami Jackfruit

Source: Muchtadi (2010) [14].

In the table above, it is seen that the nutritional content of jackfruit straw is quite good coupled with a protein content of 1.95%. It is acceptable to add protein levels, judging from the nutritional content, jackfruit straw has crude fiber that is part of dietary fiber [14].

IV. RESULT

Based on the results of research used Organoleptic and Hedonic tests, it can be explained below:

The substitution of the basic ingredients of the Floss using Dami jackfruit 100% was able to affect the color, aroma, taste, and texture.

Table 4: The Comparison of Dami Jackfruit Floss 100% and Dami Jackfruit 75% Mix with Beef floss 25%

Source: Data Processed. 2022

Based on table 4, the blue one is Dami Jackfruit Floss 100% got scores from the panelists, namely Aroma 3.2, Taste 3.49, Texture 3.58, Color 2.95 while the orange one is Dami Jackfruit Floss 75% mixed with Beef floss 25% got scores Aroma 3.87, Taste 3.27, Texture 4.13, Color 4.27.

It can see from the table, and the data, that Dami Jackfruit Floss 100%, only the taste preferred by the panelists, looks higher in value compared to Dami Jackfruit Floss 75%, and Beef floss 25%. It showed that taste of Dami Jackfruit Floss is 100% well accepted by panelists. Meanwhile, the Aroma, Color, and panelists preferred the texture of the Dami Jackfruit Floss 75% mixed with Beef floss 25%.

V. DISCUSSION

The Floss or Abon includes snacks or side dishes that are fast food. The public knows the product, The Floss made from beef is processed in such a way that it has dry and savory characteristics. The meat used in making shredded beef is beef and buffalo [10].

According to the results of research on color, 75% Dami Jackfruit Floss mixed with 25% Beef Floss is more attractive in color than 100% Dami Jackfruit Floss.

Based on the theory, factors that affect the rate or speed of the browning reaction include water content. The rate of non-enzymatic browning reactions will run slowly at low temperatures [15].

Products' color is the first thing suchlike consumers are interested in buying and tasting or eating. Therefore, the processing of meat to give it an attractive color depends on the duration and method of cooking [16]

Based on the outcome of research on aroma, the aroma of 75% Dami Jackfruit Floss mixed with 25% Beef floss is more flavorful than 100% Dami Jackfruit Floss.

It is to the theory that the insertion of spices into meat provides a significant interaction with the aroma of beef that can change the volatile compounds [17].

Aroma is the next stage after color, so consumers smell the product from its aroma. Consumer perception that the smell of food can determine the delicacy of the food [16].

We can see from the outcome of the texture of 75% Dami Jackfruit Floss mixed with 25% Beef floss is more texture than 100% Dami Jackfruit Floss.

The texture is one of the determining factors in consuming a product to determine the elasticity of a product that can assess using the sense of touching, through touching [16].

Based on Table 4, on the Tasted, panelists gave higher scores for 100% Dami Jackfruit Floss compared to 75% Dami Jackfruit Floss mixed with 25% Beef Floss. When other results on Aroma, Color, and Texture value 75% Dami Jackfruit Floss mixed with 25% Beef Floss higher. It shows that 100% Dami Jackfruit Floss has a taste acceptable to the community.

The products' taste is principal to dominant to influence consumers to buy and even purchase many times, and they can become loyal customers. The Flavour can impact the final decision of consumers to accept or reject a food product,

even though the color is attractive, the aroma is fragrant, and the texture is by the product. Consumers will refuse if when tasting the taste does not meet their taste [16]

VI. CONCLUSION

Abon produces from beef, chicken, and buffalo. With advances in food technology, shredded beef can substitute with products from animal sources such as capon, and various kinds of fish or vegetable additions, which have to investigate like papaya, banana, and cassava. In a nutshell, making abon by doing preparation, mixing spices, meat/plants, cooking, shredding, frying, and draining to dry.

Dami Jackfruit is part of Jackfruit in the form of flowers that are unfertilized. It ingests seldom and lavishly, then a trial was carried out using an organoleptic test to become Abon.

This research shows that the potential substitution of 100% Dami Jackfruit as a substitute for Beef Floss can be accepted by the public because the Taste of 100% Dami Jackfruit Floss has more advantages than Aroma, Color, and Texture at 75% Dami Jackfruit Floss mixed with 25% Beef Floss.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We favor thanking the panelists who have taken the time to fill out the questionnaire and taste the Dami Jackfruit Floss as well as to those whom we cannot mention one by one who has taken the time and are willing to be interviewed for our journal.

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